

Brand name	Tenax™
Product type	DRNF Dry Reinforcement Non-Crimp Fabric
Product key	710211 X02
Product designation	DRNF ST BD 0400 710211 X02
Variant	X02: PB1_10-STS40-BD1-Y9_TP30-0400
Construction	+45°/-45°/PB

Detail construction

Layer		Fiber	Areal weight [g/m ²]
<i>Stitch</i>	<i>Tricot-pillar</i>		
3		Powder Binder	10
2	-45°	Tenax™-E STS40 E23 24K 1600tex	200
1	+45°	Tenax™-E STS40 E23 24K 1600tex	200
<i>Stitch</i>	<i>Loop-side</i>		

+ 4 g for stitching yarn

Product features

Carbon fiber areal weight incl. sizing	400 g/m ²
Total areal weight	414 g/m ²
Fabric width	1270 mm or 2540 mm
Stitching length	3.0 mm
Paper core dimension	1400/2800 mm x 152.4 mm x 10 mm
Typical roll length	0 m - 150 m

Process parameter

- If veil based toughening technology is part of the product:
It is developed for all resin infusion processes with curing temperature of approx. 180 °C.
- If powder binder is part of the product:
The preform recommendation is to apply vacuum on preform package and hold for 20 min. at 120 °C.

- All data shown are typical values representative of the material and cannot be guaranteed. Properties may vary depending on samples preparation and test methods.
- A detailed customer specification is arranged on request.
- The export or transfer of carbon fiber products can be subject to authorization, depending on end-use and final destination.